

Package ‘sdbuscontrol’

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Title A Shiny Application Illustrating Salmonella Dublin Control

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Description What the package does (one paragraph).

License GPL (>= 3)

Encoding UTF-8

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Depends R (>= 4.1.0), tidyverse

Imports shiny, shinydashboard, shinyMatrix

Suggests knitr, rmarkdown, spelling, testthat (>= 3.0.0)

Config/testthat/edition 3

VignetteBuilder knitr

Language en-GB

LazyData true

NeedsCompilation no

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Description

What the package does (one paragraph).

Usage

```
sdubcontrol(  
  data_pop,  
  prevHerd,  
  prevAni,  
  probSamp,  
  seAni,  
  spAni,  
  nHeif,  
  nCalf,  
  nAdult,  
  nVol,  
  seClin,  
  spClin,  
  probClinInf,  
  probClin,  
  seMilk,  
  spMilk,  
  missSamp = FALSE,  
  burnin = 3  
)
```

Arguments

data_pop	input population
prevHerd	surveillance parameter
prevAni	surveillance parameter
probSamp	surveillance parameter
seAni	surveillance parameter
spAni	surveillance parameter
nHeif	surveillance parameter
nCalf	surveillance parameter
nAdult	surveillance parameter
nVol	surveillance parameter
seClin	surveillance parameter
spClin	surveillance parameter
probClinInf	surveillance parameter
probClin	surveillance parameter
seMilk	surveillance parameter
spMilk	surveillance parameter
burnin	number of burnin cycles

Details

Some description of the package

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References

Some article that you might want users to look at

See Also

[pkg_new](#) for the function that created this package

app_launch	<i>Launch shiny application</i>
------------	---------------------------------

Description

Launch shiny application

Usage

```
app_launch()
```

calfprop_hist	<i>Function for generating heifer proportion histogram</i>
---------------	--

Description

Function for generating heifer proportion histogram

Usage

```
calfprop_hist(data_pop)
```

Arguments

data_pop	input data
----------	------------

CattleDenmark

Data summarising cattle herds in Denmark

Description

A data frame containing summary statistics

Usage

```
data(CattleDenmark)
```

Format

A data frame with 6 rows and 14 variables:

CalfProp_alpha

CalfProp_beta

CalfProp_mean

CalfProp_sd

CattleYears_meanlog

CattleYears_sdlog

Freq

HeifProp_alpha

HeifProp_beta

HeifProp_mean

HeifProp_sd

HerdTypeID

HerdTypeText

Prop

generate_cattle_population

Generate cattle herd population function

Description

Generate cattle herd population function

Usage

```
generate_cattle_population(N, matrix_distr)
```

Arguments

N number of herds

matrix_distr herd size distribution by type

heifprop_hist	<i>Function for generating heifer proportion histogram</i>
---------------	--

Description

Function for generating heifer proportion histogram

Usage

```
heifprop_hist(data_pop)
```

Arguments

data_pop	input data
----------	------------

herdsize_hist	<i>Function for generating herd size histogram</i>
---------------	--

Description

Function for generating herd size histogram

Usage

```
herdsize_hist(data_pop)
```

Arguments

data_pop	input data
----------	------------

herdtype_bar	<i>Function for generating herd type bar chart</i>
--------------	--

Description

Function for generating herd type bar chart

Usage

```
herdtype_bar(data_pop)
```

Arguments

data_pop	input data
----------	------------

leveltype_bar	<i>Function for generating herd type level bar chart</i>
---------------	--

Description

Function for generating herd type level bar chart

Usage

```
leveltype_bar(data_level)
```

Arguments

data_level	input data
------------	------------

level_cross_table	<i>Function for generating cross table for overall population</i>
-------------------	---

Description

Function for generating cross table for overall population

Usage

```
level_cross_table(data_level)
```

Arguments

data_level	input data
------------	------------

level_type	<i>Function for generating herd type level table</i>
------------	--

Description

Function for generating herd type level table

Usage

```
level_type(data_level)
```

Arguments

data_level	input data
------------	------------

sampfreq_table *Function for generating sample frequency table*

Description

Function for generating sample frequency table

Usage

sampfreq_table(data_level)

Arguments

data_level input data

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